

D8.3: Dissemination Pack

WP8 – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

Document Information

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1 Executive summary

The project hackAIR joins the movement to improve air quality data in Europe through participatory sensing and citizen engagement. hackAIR builds an open technology platform that citizens can use to access, collect and improve air quality information in Europe.

As part of its activities to disseminate and communicate the project, its activities and results, a number of materials have been prepared. This document includes the full set of dissemination and communication material for the hackAIR project in October 2016. The following materials are available:

Title	Date of availability
Visual identity and branding	31 March 2016
Postcards	19 May 2016
Presentation	24 May 2016
Brochure	30 June 2016
Poster	1 September 2016
Website	28 March 2016
Newsletter – Issue 1	11 April 2016
Newsletter – Issue 2	20 October 2016
Social Media	20 December 2015

All communications materials are available for download from www.hackair.eu/downloads.

2 Visual identity and branding

The visual identity aims to provide guidelines that will help all hackAIR project partners build a strong and consistent branding, messages and visuals for hackAIR. The visual identity guidelines below were included in D8.1 Communication and dissemination strategy; they replace the initial guidance included in deliverable D1.2 Project management handbook.

Visual identity guidelines are available for public download from <http://www.hackair.eu/downloads>. The logo files are available at the same address.

Figure 2.1 Visual identity guide

WHEN TO USE WHICH VERSION OF THE LOGO

IT'S A MATTER OF JUDGEMENT MAINLY. IF YOU CAN'T READ IT, YOU CAN'T USE IT. BUT LET'S HAVE SOME LOOSE GUIDELINES.

PRINTED MATTER

START USING THE LOGO WITHOUT THE TAGLINE WHEN THE TOTAL WIDTH IS LESS THAN 20mm.

START USING THE SMALL LOGO WHEN THE TOTAL WIDTH IS LESS THAN 11mm.

MINIMUM SIZE USE OF THE SMALL LOGO IS 6mm WIDTH.

ONLINE

START USING THE LOGO WITHOUT THE TAGLINE WHEN THE TOTAL WIDTH IS LESS THAN 120px.

START USING THE SMALL LOGO WHEN THE HACKAIR WORD'S WIDTH IS LESS THAN 60px.

MINIMUM SIZE USE OF THE SMALL LOGO IS 40px WIDTH.

THE COLORS

COLOR 1 [Primary]

R: 255 G: 102 B: 102 #FF6666 C: 0 M: 75 Y: 50 K: 0

COLOR 2 [Alternative for dark backgrounds]

R: 255 G: 255 B: 195 #FFFFC3 C: 0 M: 0 Y: 30 K: 0

GREY [Secondary]

R: 77 G: 77 B: 77 #4D4D4D C: 0 M: 0 Y: 0 K: 85

USE WHITE IF NEEDED, TO REPLACE THE GREY COLOR. ON A DARK BACKGROUND E.G.

FOR BACKGROUND COLOR, USE GREY OR COLORS

R: 0 G: 163 B: 172 #00A3AC C: 80 M: 10 Y: 35 K: 0

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COLLECTIVE AWARENESS FOR AIR QUALITY

A

THE FONTS

Calibri

CALIBRI CAN BE FOUND IN MOST SYSTEMS. USE IT FOR YOUR BODY TEXT. IF CALIBRI ISN'T INSTALLED IN YOUR SYSTEM, YOU CAN USE **TREBUCHET MS** AS AN ALTERNATIVE.

Century

USE **CENTURY BOLD** FOR THE TITLE TEXT ONLY. IN **COLORI**. IF CENTURY ISN'T INSTALLED IN YOUR SYSTEM, YOU CAN USE **TIMES** AS AN ALTERNATIVE.

BookendsWithAccents

LOGO IS BASED ON THIS FONT. NEVER USE IT, EXCEPT IN CALL FOR ACTION TAGS. AS A DIRECT CONNECTION TO OUR LOGO. YOU MIGHT NEED TO ADD AN OUTLINE TO MAKE IT THICKER. YOU CAN FIND IT HERE: <http://www.fontspace.com/Intestingrogru/bookendswithaccents> PLEASE SUPPORT THE FONT DESIGNER.

GEOMETR451BLACK

IT'S USED FOR THE TAGLINE ONLY.

Illustrations

In addition to the visual identity, hackAIR has developed a graphic style of illustrations. A few examples:

Figure 2.2 Selected illustrations for hackAIR

3 Communications material

Postcards

As a first printed product, hackAIR produced a set of simple postcards for all partners in time for the start of the co-creation workshops. 1.000 copies were printed and distributed to partners at the second consortium meeting in May 2016.

A digital version of the postcard is available for download from <http://www.hackair.eu/downloads>.

Figure 3.1 hackAIR postcard, front and back

Presentation

A standard presentation is available for use for all project partners, explaining the purpose of the project, its outputs and ways of working to external audiences. The presentation is available for download in both 16:9 and 4:3 screen format from <http://www.hackair.eu/downloads>. In addition, the presentation is published on the Slideshare platform at <http://www.slideshare.net/hackAIR>.

Figure 3.2 Complete hackAIR presentation deck

Slide 1: Title Slide
 hackAIR
 Open technology platform
 Collect, access and improve air quality information in Europe

Slide 2: Premature Deaths
 In 2011, 458.000 premature deaths in Europe were attributed to particulate matter in the air.

Slide 3: Air pollution: invisible but dangerous
 Up to a third of Europeans living in cities are exposed to air pollutant levels exceeding EU air quality standards. Around 88% of the urban population is exposed to excessive Particulate Matter (PM₁₀) levels and other pollutants deemed damaging to health by the World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines.

Standard	Percentage of EU Urban Population Exposed
EU limit values	33%
WHO guidelines	88%

Slide 4: Increasing citizens' engagement on air quality
 • Air pollution is the single environmental issue Europeans worry about the most (56%)¹
 • Nearly six out of ten Europeans do not feel informed about air quality issues in their country (59%)²

Slide 5: We need better information
 To provide useful estimates of air quality, we need to:
 • Fill gaps in areas where distances between sites may be large;
 • Improve access to data across many sources;
 • Provide up to date air quality information.

Slide 6: Time to be proactive
 Individually: protecting our health & the environment
 Collectively: triggering policy change & encouraging behavioral change towards a cleaner air

Slide 7: 6 partners, 5 European countries
 We are taking up the challenge to launch the hackAIR project!
 hackAIR is all about awareness and behavioral change: taking care of our health and of the earth.

Slide 8: Footer
 Joining the movement to improve air quality data in Europe
 DRAXIS, NIU, CERTH, BUND, QNSUBJECT

hackAIR partners

DRAXIS, Greece
Project management and platform integration

NILU, Norway
Data fusion model and pilot test in Norway

CERTH, Greece
Data discovery and integration

DRAXIS, Greece
Project management and platform integration

NILU, Norway
Data fusion model and pilot test in Norway

CERTH, Greece
Data discovery and integration

BUND, Germany
Pilot test in Germany and network of interest

VUB, Belgium
Co-creation and engagement strategies

ON-SUBJECT, Netherlands
Dissemination and exploitation

BUND, Germany
Pilot test in Germany and network of interest

VUB, Belgium
Co-creation and engagement strategies

ON-SUBJECT, Netherlands
Dissemination and exploitation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019718

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Making the problem visible

"The biggest strength of hackAIR is making air quality visible. You can be informed and contribute to this yourself." Arne Fellermann, BUND

Its uniqueness:

- Openness (open source);
- Pictures as measurement tool;
- Easy to use hardware hack solutions

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019718

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What happens when you combine open technology, participatory sensing and air quality in Europe?

Photo: Austin Bar, Unsplash

Meet Aylin!

Should I ride the bicycle or take the tram today?

I'm helping to map the neighbourhood's air by taking pictures.

It's really interesting to see how air quality changes over time – and to compare with other cities!

End users & stakeholders

Organisations working on public health and/or environmental issues

ASTMA-DG ALLERGI FORBUNDET

Institutions conducting research and monitoring on air quality and pollution

SMART CITIZEN

CAPTOR

Businesses and projects collecting, managing, and displaying air quality data

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019718

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hackAIR in a nutshell

Data Sources: MOBILE IMAGES, OPEN HARDWARE SENSOR, LOW-TECH MEASUREMENTS, OPEN AIR QUALITY DATASETS

Data Integration → Data fusion

Access to:

- Open source code;
- Real-time information on the current status of air quality;
- A community of like-minded users;
- Personalised recommendations.

Data Access

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019718

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Data sources: Mobile images

- From Instagram or as a direct upload in the hackAIR app
- Pictures need:
 - Geolocation data
 - Sufficient visibility of clear sky
- hackAIR's algorithm then estimates particle matter content based on the colour of the sky using aerosol optical depth

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019718

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Data sources: Open hardware sensors

- Tutorials and manuals for a DIY-sensor kit from low-cost hardware, including:
 - Arduino libraries for quick and easy deployment
 - Stand-alone hackAIR sensor system based on PSoC® with Bluetooth Low Energy transceiver
 - Optical air quality sensors to measure PM₁₀
 - Estimated system cost: ca. 40-90€

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019718

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Data sources: Low-tech measurements

- Simple setup: Aquarium pump + food container + paper filter
- Upload smartphone photo of the resulting colored paper and a reference filter
- hackAIR estimates air pollution based on relative difference of filter colors

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019718

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Data sources: Open air quality datasets and data integration

hackAIR integrates publicly available data sources from air quality monitoring stations and participatory sensing initiatives to provide an approximate picture of the current air quality in a given location.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019718

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Towards engagement & behaviour change

hackAIR helps citizens to move from awareness to behaviour change on air quality:

- Members of the hackAIR community collaborate to gather and make sense of air quality data;
- The platform supports citizens with:
 1. Steps to reduce individual air pollution, and
 2. Steps to protect oneself against air pollution;
- The data can also be used to impact policy making towards air quality improvements.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019714

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Co-creation of hackAIR

Together with users, developers and stakeholders in Norway, Germany, Greece

The innovation border approach (Jacobs et al., 2014)

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hackAIR pilots

Starting in September 2016 in two countries:

- **Germany:** Focus on environmental activists
- **Norway:** Focus on health interest groups

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019714

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hackAIR timeline

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019714

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Join a growing movement to improve air quality data

Visit our website: www.hackair.eu

Sign up to the hackAIR newsletter: <http://bit.ly/hackair-news>

(ADD ONE MORE CURRENT OPPORTUNITY OR DELETE THIS BUBBLE)

Follow us on Twitter: @hack_AIR

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019714

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Thank you!

[Presenter's contact details]

Project coordinator: Dr. Machi Simeonidou, msimeonidou@draxis.gr
 Media contact: Wiebke Herding, wiebke@onsubject.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019714

Brochure

In June 2016, hackAIR produced a 6-page brochure about the project. 1.500 copies of the brochure were printed and distributed to all partners.

A digital copy of the brochure is available for download from <http://www.hackair.eu/downloads>.

Figure 3.3 hackAIR brochure

What's in it for you?

Improving air quality in Europe requires action on many levels: from citizens and NGOs to policy makers.

hackAIR will enable communities of citizens to: map their neighbourhood's air by taking pictures of the sky; provide measurements themselves, through easy-to-build open hardware sensors; and see how air quality changes over time – and compare with other cities.

“The biggest strength of hackAIR is in making air pollution visible. You can be informed and contribute to this with hackAIR!”

Arne Fellermann, BUND

The technology developed will be of interest to policy makers, educators and technology enthusiasts: everybody can use it to manage their own air quality monitoring station - and help others learn about DIY sensing.

Individuals can use the information to:

- avoid polluting behaviour (e.g. through their choice of transport);
- reduce their exposure to air pollution (e.g. by deciding or adjusting the time and route of travel);

or

- participate in the public discourse on improved air quality (e.g. by writing letters to policymakers).

Scientists and policy makers can use the resulting air quality data to:

- gain insights on air quality patterns;

and

- inform public policy.

For 2017, we are looking for organisations interested in hosting local hackAIR workshops to build awareness of air quality and explore the technology in practice. Contact us!

www.hackAIR.eu

Join the movement to improve air quality data in Europe!

Contact

Website: www.hackAIR.eu
 Email: info@hackAIR.eu
 Twitter: @hack_AIR
 Newsletter: bit.ly/hackair-news

Project coordinator:
 Dr. Machi Simeonidou, msimeonidou@draxis.gr

Media contact:
 Wiebke Herding, wiebke@onsubject.eu

Project timeline

- January 2016: Start of hackAIR project
- August 2017: First version of hackAIR platform available
- September 2017: Pilot tests start in Germany and Norway
- October 2018: Final version of hackAIR platform available
- December 2018: End of hackAIR project

Partners

DRAXIS, NILU, CERTH, BUND, ONSUBJECT

Affiliated organisations

www.hackAIR.eu

Poster

To support hackAIR's presence at events and conferences, we prepared a poster in September 2016. Where specific requirements exist, e.g. at scientific conferences, custom posters can be prepared, too.

All versions of the hackAIR poster are available for download from <http://www.hackair.eu/downloads>.

Figure 3.4 hackAIR poster

Poster prepared for the CIENS Urban Conference (Oct 2016)

Poster prepared for the European Cooperation in Science and Technology (Oct 2016)

Collective awareness platform for outdoor air pollution - the hackAIR approach

Concept
hackAIR is an open technology platform to access, collect and improve information on air quality (AQ) in Europe. It combines official AQ data with community-driven data sources.

Data sources

- Easy-to-build open hardware sensor modules
- AQ information derived from mobile phone pictures of the sky and webcams
- Low-tech measurement set-up involving paper filters and aquarium air pumps
- Publicly available AQ data

Data access

- Web application for local air quality information
- Mobile app to access air quality information or contribute own measurements

Participatory sensing and citizen engagement

- Citizen involvement through own requirements and publishing of outdoor air quality levels
- Co-design approaches for designing the hackAIR platform

Impacts
Improving AQ data in Europe through integrating existing and new obtained data.
Engaging citizens directly in measuring outdoor AQ levels in Germany and Norway.
Raising awareness about AQ and encouraging behavioural changes amongst citizens.

hackAIR partners: NILU, DRAXIS, CERTH, BUND, Wip University of Applied Sciences, QNSUBJECT.

Project information: Coordinator: Dr. Machi Simeonidou, Environmental S.A. (DRAXIS), Greece, machisimeonidou@draxis.gr, Website: www.hackair.eu, Contact: info@hackair.eu

hackAIR: a Collective Awareness Platform for Outdoor Air Pollution

Overview
Developing an open technology platform that users can use to access, collect and improve information on air quality in Europe. It consists of:
1. A customisable web application for local air quality information
2. A mobile app that citizens can use to access to air quality information or contribute measurement

Impacts
Improve air quality data in Europe through participatory sensing technology and citizen engagement.
Facilitate citizens to access air quality information in Europe by using hackAIR web application and a mobile app.
Engage citizens directly in measuring outdoor air quality levels in Norway and Germany.
Empower citizens via a range of activities from data collection, to knowledge exchange with stakeholders, using hackAIR tools for collaborative sensing and mapping, behavioural changes surveys, and information decision-making.

Sustainability

Indicator of success	Germany	Norway	Total
No. of additional open users interested in adopting hackAIR	7610	3781	11391
% of additional citizens interested in adopting hackAIR	80	48	64
% of companies interested in using hackAIR open data for development	10	4	14
% of additional NGOs (not business organisations) interested in adopting hackAIR	5		

Pilot in Norway and Germany

Indicator of success	Germany	Norway	Total
No. of hackAIR community members in pilot areas	4520	1120	5640
hackAIR users participating in AQ data (open data) collection	620	1270	1890
hackAIR users participating in AQ data (open data) collection	200	50	250

Partners: DRAXIS, NILU, CERTH, BUND, Wip University of Applied Sciences, QNSUBJECT.

Duration: January, 2016 – December 2018
Coordinator: Dr. Machi Simeonidou, Environmental S.A. (DRAXIS), Greece, machisimeonidou@draxis.gr, Website: www.hackair.eu, Contact: info@hackair.eu

4 Online Communications

Website

hackAIR's website was set up in March 2016 in line with the plans of the hackAIR communications and dissemination strategy. It is located at www.hackAIR.eu and based on the content management system Wordpress. The hackAIR website uses the following structure:

About	How it works	News and events	Resources	Contact
About hackAIR	Air quality	News and updates	Downloads	
Partners	Technology	Workshops and events	Related projects	
Timeline	Co-creation and engagement	hackAIR newsletter		
	Data sources			

Figure 4.1 hackAIR.eu: Homepage

hackAIR

COLLECTIVE AWARENESS FOR AIR QUALITY

ABOUT HOW IT WORKS NEWS AND EVENTS RESOURCES CONTACT

Collective awareness for air quality

hackAIR is an open technology platform for citizen observatories on air quality, to raise collective awareness about the levels of human exposure to air pollution. Use it to access, collect and improve information about air pollution levels where you live.

ABOUT THE PROJECT

"Air pollution is the single environmental issue Europeans worry about the most, and many do not feel sufficiently informed about air quality issues in their country.

Air pollution, and more specifically particulate matter, shortens people's lifespan and contributes to serious illnesses such as heart disease, respiratory problems and cancer."

Arne Fellermann, air quality campaigner for Friends of the Earth Germany (BUND)

In the coming three years, we're creating and testing an open platform that will enable citizens and organisations to easily engage in generating and publishing information relevant to outdoor air pollution. We will do this by leveraging the power of citizen science, online social networks, mobile and open hardware technologies, and engagement strategies.

hackAIR will provide citizens with improved information about air pollution levels where they live. This will be useful for people who like to exercise outside, look after children or the elderly or suffer from respiratory problems. It will also allow for a conversation in the local community about possible improvements in air quality.

FIND OUT HOW IT WORKS

Project Partners

DRAXIS ENVIRONMENTAL TECHNOLOGIES

NLU

CERTH

BUND

Vrije Universiteit Brussel

QNSUBJECT

Figure 4.2 Selected screenshots of the hackAIR website, October 2016

Workshops and events
Engagement and collaboration are at the heart of hackAIR's activities. That is why we make an effort to connect with other organisations and communities working on air quality and participatory sensing. In the coming months, we will organize workshops for citizens in multiple European cities.

You can meet us at the following occasions:

Upcoming events

Organised by hackAIR	External events with hackAIR participation
19 October 2016: hackAIR co-creation workshop (Oslo, Norway) As a follow-up on a previous workshop in June we will present first ideas for both design and functionalities, after which we discuss with the participants whether their requirements have been met or not and how to further improve the hackAIR platform.	13 October 2016: CIENS Urban Conference: Smart and green cities - for whom! (Oslo, Norway) with NILU
20 October 2016: hackAIR co-creation workshop 1 (Berlin, Germany)	13-14 October 2016: Mapping, Sensing, and Crowdsourcing Geographic Information (London, UK) with NILU
3 November 2016: Inaugural meeting of the Air Sensing Network (Berlin, Germany)	18 October 2016: Round table 'citizen air quality meter' (Brussels, Belgium) with VUB
10 November 2016: hackAIR co-creation workshop 2 (Berlin, Germany)	8 November 2016: European Stakeholder Round Table on Citizen and DIY Science and Responsible Research and Innovation (Berlin, Germany) with BUND
24-25 November 2016: hackAIR project meeting (Brussels, Belgium)	14 November 2016: Workshop (Un)plugging Data in Smart City-Regions (Brussels, Belgium) with VUB, ON-SUBJECT
	1-2 February 2017: Digital Social Innovation Fair 2017 (Rome, Italy) with Draxix
	23-28 April 2017: European Geosciences Union General Assembly 2017 (Vienna, Austria) TBC

Past events

Organised by hackAIR	External events with hackAIR participation
11-12 January 2016: hackAIR kick-off meeting (Thessaloniki, Greece) Project announcement	17-22 April 2016: European Geosciences Union General Assembly 2016 (Vienna, Austria) with NILU
27 April 2016: hackAIR introduction webinar (online) Invitation Presentation (pdf)	22 April 2016: Making Sense. Advances and explorations in participatory sensing during the Design and the City conference (Amsterdam, Netherlands) with ON-SUBJECT
30-31 May 2016: hackAIR project meeting (Berlin, Germany)	9-13 May 2016: Living Planet Symposium 2016 (Prague, Czech Republic) with NILU
21 June 2016: hackAIR co-creation workshop (Oslo, Norway) The workshop was organized to engage with citizens to discuss their experiences regarding measuring and retrieving air quality information. We evaluated existing air quality platforms with the aim to sketch the ideal air quality platform, based on the needs and requirements of the workshop participants.	17 May 2016: 1st International Workshop on the Social Web for Environmental and Ecological Monitoring (SWEEK) with CERTH
27 June 2016: hackAIR co-creation workshop (Berlin, Germany) In this workshop we engage with citizens to discuss their experiences regarding measuring and retrieving air quality information. What should the hackAIR platform look like?	18 May 2016: CAPS community meeting and workshop (Berlin, Germany) with DRAXIS
	18 May 2016: Technology Forum 2016 (Thessaloniki, Greece) with CERTH, DRAXIS
	19-21 May 2016: The ECSA Citizen Science Conference 2016 (Berlin, Germany) with DRAXIS, NILU
	31 May - 2 June 2016: GED European Projects Workshop (Berlin, Germany) with NILU
	1 June 2016: 10th GED European Projects Workshop (Berlin, Germany) with NILU
	7-10 June 2016: Citizen Observatories for Water Management (COWM) workshop (Venice, Italy) with NILU
	29 June 2016: CAPS Policy Workshop on Digital Social Innovation organised by the DSHEU (Brussels, Belgium) with VUB
	1-4 September 2016: 18th Annual conference International Society for Environmental Epidemiology (ISEE) (Rome, Italy) with NILU
	10 September 2016: Eindhoven Maker Faire (Eindhoven, Netherlands) with ON-SUBJECT
	12-14 September 2016: 1st International Workshop on Internet and Social Media for Environmental Monitoring (ISEM 2016) during 3rd International Conference on Internet Science (Florence, Italy) with CERTH and DRAXIS
	26-27 September 2016: ICT Proposers' Day (Bratislava, Slovakia) with Draxix

The hackAIR project

hackAIR is an EU-funded project aiming to develop an open technology platform for citizen observatories on air quality. It is supported through the EU programme on "Collective Awareness Platforms for Sustainability and Social Innovation" until December 2018.

Following a co-creation process with users and the development of the hackAIR platform and its components, the hackAIR platform will be pilot tested in Norway and Germany starting in September 2017 in order to validate the service platform and contribute towards individual and collective awareness about air quality in Europe, encouraging changes in behaviour towards air quality improvements.

By pilot testing the hackAIR platform and related collective sensing tools, the project aims to raise collective awareness about the daily levels of human exposure to air pollution.

Why hackAIR

Air pollution is an environmental issue with serious health and lifespan implications. However, it remains difficult for citizens to assess their exposure to air pollution and air quality issues in their country. Official air quality sensors are often few and far between, coverage is poor outside cities, and their data is not always easily accessible.

The hackAIR platform

The hackAIR open platform will enable communities of citizens to easily engage their members in generating and publishing information relevant to outdoor air pollution, leveraging the power of citizen science, online social networks, mobile and open hardware technologies, and engagement strategies.

hackAIR aims to complement official data with community-driven data sources, for collecting, analysing and sharing air quality measurements to community members through low-cost open hardware sensors easily assembled by citizens, web and/or mobile phones.

Users

hackAIR will engage communities of citizens in generating and publishing information relevant to outdoor air pollution including:

Citizens (e.g. elderly, parents of small children, outdoor sport enthusiasts, conservationists) and app/service developers.	Can submit data through the hackAIR platform.
Open source community and operators of personal weather stations.	Can build an air quality monitoring station.
Organisations, environmental organizations, health associations, makerspaces, educational organizations.	Can organise local hackAIR workshops to build awareness.
Scientific community (universities, research institutes, NGOs, independent researchers).	Can use data to gain insights on air quality patterns; use hackAIR platform and communication channels for dialogue.
Enterprises interested in hackAIR products and services for other health related apps, etc.	Can use products and services created by hackAIR.
Local government and transport-related agencies.	Can use data to inform public policy.

Benefits

Citizens benefit from the platform through easy engagement and participation in monitoring atmospheric PM₁₀ receiving real-time information on the current status of air quality, participating in a community of like-minded users who are concerned about the effects of air pollution, receiving personalised recommendations on actions that they can perform as individual members.

Ready to contribute?

GET INVOLVED FIND OUT HOW IT WORKS

"Air quality is mostly an invisible issue: it should never become so bad that you can see it. hackAIR is European, it has all these different sources, it's an open platform. But really: most people don't even know that air quality monitoring systems exist, so in its core hackAIR is all about awareness. It's about taking care of the earth." (Paulien Coppens, VUB)

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How it works

hackAIR will enable communities of citizens to easily engage their members in generating and publishing information relevant to outdoor air pollution.

hackAIR takes advantage of existing open and complementary community-driven data that is then processed to extract and normalize information for collective awareness for air quality in Europe.

- Air quality
- Participatory sensing technology
- Co-creation & engagement
- Data sources

Data Sources

EXTERNAL MANAGERMENTS INGESTION MOBILE APP MEASUREMENTS SOCIAL MEDIA MINING hackAIR OPENNET MEASUREMENTS

Web & Mobile App

- Web and mobile app: User-generated images acquired via the hackAIR mobile app.
- Social media images: Images shared online and publicly available in social networks.
- Open hardware sensors: Easy-to-assemble open hardware sensors that can be built anywhere.
- Open data: Easy-to-assemble open hardware sensors that can be built anywhere and by any citizen.

ABOUT HACKAIR

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LATEST TWEETS

Our newsletter is out! Check our technology update, where to meet us, how to use hackAIR and an update from the tea...
<https://twitter.com/mhaklay/788795590331146240>

And we are in London today #costivi! Thanks for sharing @mhaklay
<https://twitter.com/mhaklay/status/786582451342741504>

And you can discuss #airquality #monitoring with @AFellermann in 2 co-creation workshops, 20 Oct & 10 Nov in Berlin <http://bit.ly/2eeK5Uv>

Follow @hack_air.

SIGN UP FOR NEWS AND UPDATES

Email Address*

First Name

Last Name

* = required field

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Related projects

Many initiatives and projects are working on participatory approaches to improve air quality information worldwide. Together, we can make sure that citizens and municipalities get the information they need to improve air quality where they live.

While hackAIR's platform will only be available in Summer 2017, you can already check out the following related projects and tools.

Show all

- Making Sense**: Advances and experiments in participatory sensing. Making Sense EU (H2020) seeks to empower citizens through personal digital manufacturing applied to... 13th June 2016
- Smart Citizen**: Open source technology to generate participatory processes of people in the cities. Connecting data, people and knowledge, the objective of... 13th June 2016
- HabitatMap**: HabitatMap is a non-profit environmental health justice organization, building online mapping and a social networking platform to support grassroots environmental... 13th June 2016
- AirVisual**: Air Visual provides home air quality monitors revealing invisible threats indoors and out... 8th April 2016
- CAPTOR**: CAPTOR will engage a network of local communities for monitoring tropospheric ozone pollution and... 22nd March 2016
- iSPEX**: iSPEX is an innovative way to measure aerosols. Aerosols have an enormous impact on our lives... 22nd March 2016
- Plume Labs**: Makers of the Plume #AirReport, urban weather forecast and environmental AI to beat air pollution in... 22nd March 2016
- CITI-SENSE**: CITI-SENSE will develop "citizens' observatories" to empower citizens to contribute to and participate in... 22nd March 2016
- Mapping for Change**: Mapping for Change has supported many communities across London to measure and map local air quality... 22nd March 2016
- iSCAPE**: engineers from Trinity College Dublin will deploy next-gen environmental living labs in cities across Europe to improve air quality... 22nd March 2016

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Newsletter

hackAIR compiles a biannual newsletter for stakeholders and other interested parties with news about the project, related initiatives and interesting developments in the area of air quality and participatory sensing. Two issues were published in April and October 2016. A sign up form is available on the hackAIR website.

Figure 4.3 hackAIR newsletter April and October 2016

Social Media

hackAIR focuses its social media engagement on Twitter at this stage, building a network of influencers and supporters around participatory sensing and air quality.

Follow hackAIR at https://twitter.com/hack_air.

Figure 4.4 hackAIR Twitter feed

5 Upcoming Items

The current set of materials available in this dissemination pack are suitable to promote the project and its activities during the development and startup phase.

Once the technology platform is available and users are invited to set up their own sensors and contribute data, additional material will be required, including:

- **An online tutorial** for event organisers and users of the hackAIR platform showing how the hackAIR platform works will be available on the website. It will be uploaded to social media for additional exposure.
- **A video** for event organisers and project partners to inform and engage the wider community by showing results of the project. The video will include background information, interactive stories and will be available on the website and uploaded to social media (Youtube) for additional exposure.

